

Special issue call for papers: “Research methods in management: advances and applications”

The discussions about the importance and criticality of research methods for developing management theory as a field are not new (House,1963). Hence, the search for new and better ways of improving research quality in management has been the target of several scholars, who have tried to bring innovative alternatives for the scientific community.

Within this spirit, the *RAUSP Management Journal* is announcing the launching of a Call for Papers for its special issue “Research Methods in Management: advances and applications”. The purpose of this special issue is to foster and spread advancements in both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies in the field of management studies.

In this special issue, we seek papers that address mainly new or recent non-mainstream methodological approaches in the field of management research and their potential contribution to both scholars and students. These papers should focus on the creative description of methodologies or on the process of doing research rather than on its outcomes (if any). We also invite critical reflections about important methodological issues, including ethical and social impacts, different types of researchers’ engagement with empirical reality and different relationships between researchers and researched. Preferably, this special issue will gather contributions from leading scholars in both qualitative and quantitative research.

As guest editors for this issue, we have invited Professor Marlei Pozzebon (HEC Montréal, Canada/Fundação Getúlio Vargas - Escola de Administração do Estado de São Paulo, Brazil) and Professor Diógenes de Souza Bido (Mackenzie Presbyterian University, Brazil). Professor Pozzebon is in charge of managing the selection and reviewing processes for qualitative studies, while Professor Bido will deal with the quantitative articles. Both are well known for their expertise in those fields.

Manuscripts are expected to be submitted by May 10, 2019, and the publication is scheduled for October 2019 (*RAUSP Management Journal* 54, v4) or earlier, through the ahead of print process.

For further information regarding the submission procedures and other details, please follow the link for the call for papers.

Besides this important news, we are also very pleased to announce that the *RAUSP Management Journal* has just been approved for inclusion in Scopus, after the evaluation by Scopus Content Selection & Advisory Board (CSAB). We expect the final procedures for our journal to be listed on Scopus will be completed by May 2019.

This may be the first step for the *RAUSP Management Journal* to be acknowledged as a high-quality international journal. Regardless of this achievement, we are sure that

we need to pursue even better and higher standards. We do count on our authors, reviewers and readers to accomplish these goals in the future. We also thank all of them for what they have done so far.

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Reference

House, R. J. (1963), Research criteria and methods for the development of management theory. *Academy of Management Proceedings*, pp. 7–13.